

Determination of Activity Solubility Products of Sparingly Soluble Salts using Membrane Electrode

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MUKHERJEE¹ *et al.* determined the activity solubility products of sulphates, carbonates and oxalates of calcium and barium employing cation exchange resin membranes. They assumed the activities of both cations and anions to be the same in case of symmetrical electrolytes

However, it is possible to evaluate K_s directly from the e.m.f. value of a cell of the following type using two membrane electrodes, one cationic and the other anionic.

Calomel Electrode	Aq.-soln. of a salt having the cation (M)	Satd. soln. of M_2A	Aq.-soln. of a salt having the anion (A)	Calomel Electrode
	(I) Cationic Membrane	(II) Anionic Membrane	(III)	

If the salt is of the type MA , the overall cell potential is given by

$$E = \frac{RT}{Z_1F} \ln \frac{(a_M)_I}{(a_M)_{II}} + \frac{RT}{Z_2F} \ln \frac{(a_A)_{III}}{(a_A)_{II}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where the first term gives the potential generated across the cationic membrane and the second term gives that across the anionic membrane.

The eqn. (1) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{ZEF}{2.303 RT} = \log \frac{(a_M)_I(a_A)_{III}}{(a_M)_{II}(a_A)_{II}} = \log \frac{(a_M)_I(a_A)_{III}}{K_s} \quad \dots (2)$$

where K_s is the activity solubility product of MA ;

$$\text{or, } \log K_s = \log (a_M)_I(a_A)_{III} - \frac{ZEF}{2.303 RT} \quad \dots (3)$$

From this eqn. K_s can be easily evaluated if $(a_M)_I$, $(a_A)_{III}$ are known and E is measured.

If the electrolyte is of the type M_2A , the overall cell potential can be expressed as

$$E = \frac{RT}{Z_1F} \ln \frac{(a_M)_I}{(a_M)_{II}} + \frac{RT}{Z_2F} \ln \frac{(a_A)_{III}}{(a_A)_{II}} \quad \dots (4)$$

As, $Z_2 = 2Z_1$, rewriting the eqn. (4) as,

$$E = \frac{2.303 RT}{Z_2F} \left[\log \left\{ \frac{(a_M)_I}{(a_M)_{II}} \right\}^2 + \log \frac{(a_A)_{III}}{(a_A)_{II}} \right]$$

$$= \frac{2.303 RT}{Z_2F} \log \frac{(a_M)_I^2(a_A)_{III}}{K_s}$$

when $K_s = (a_M)_{II}^2(a_A)_{II}$;

$$\log K_s = \log \{(a_M)_I^2(a_A)_{III}\} - \frac{Z_2EF}{2.303 RT} \quad \dots (5)$$

For electrolyte of the type MA_2 , the final eqn will be

$$\log K_s = \log \{(a_M)_I(a_A)^2_{III}\} - \frac{Z_1EF}{2.303 RT} \quad \dots (6)$$

In the present note, the activity solubility products of $BaSO_4$ and $BaCrO_4$ were determined. The cation and anion exchange resins used were Dowex-50WX8 and Dowex-IX8 respectively. The membranes were prepared as usual². The anionic membrane was found to produce fairly good results with SO_4^{2-} and CrO_4^{2-} ions in aqueous solutions upto a maximum concentration of 0.0027 m. The Dowex-50WX8 membrane behaved well towards Ba^{+2} ion upto a maximum concentration of 0.0081 m in aqueous solution. $BaSO_4$ and $BaCrO_4$ were prepared by precipitating them from aqueous solution of $BaCl_2$ with K_2SO_4 and K_2CrO_4 solutions respectively. The precipitated salts were then washed repeatedly with hot water to remove the soluble impurities. The ppt. was then boiled with double distilled water and then cooled. The insoluble part was allowed to settle down at the bottom of the solution. The two membrane tubes were then dipped in the clear supernate and two tiny calomel electrodes were dipped into the solutions of the membrane tubes. The solutions in the cation and anion membrane tubes had their cation and anion respectively common with those of the sparingly soluble salts. The e.m.f. of the cell was then determined.

Results

Sparingly Soluble Salt	Room temperature = 27°		Observed E.M.F. in mv	K _s
	Inside Solution			
	Cation Chamber (I)	Anion Chamber (III)		
	$a_{Ba^{+2}}$	$a_{SO_4^{--}}$		
BaSO ₄	.001158	.00114	118.0	1.43×10^{-10}
	.001642	.00146	127.0	1.30×10^{-10}
		a_{CrO_4}		
BaCrO ₄	.001158	.001792	116.4	2.56×10^{-10}
	.004373	.001792	135.5	2.20×10^{-10}

The values of K_s calculated from the observed cell potentials are comparable to those obtained earlier by other methods³. In this method, the anion activity was not assumed to be the same as that of the cation even in the case of symmetrical electrolytes.

References

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Complexes of Dibenzoyl Sulphide with the Halides of Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury(II)

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VERY little is known about the donor properties of dibenzoyl sulphide (Bz_2S_2) which has two donor sites namely, two carbonyl groups and one sulphur—sulphur bond. Some complexes of Bz_2S_2 with nitrogen bases are known¹ but the structural evidence is lacking. Recently some seven membered ring chelates of cobalt (II) and nickel (II) with Bz_2S_2 have been isolated and characterised² wherein both the carbonyl oxygen atoms have been shown to act as the donor groups. We now report the complexes of Bz_2S_2 with halides of zinc, cadmium and mercury (II) and an attempt has been made to elucidate their structures.

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All these complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of both the components in dry benzene when both the components went into the solution. The compounds were recovered by adding an inert solvent such as petroleum ether. The composition of these compounds has been determined by elemental analysis and is reported in Table 1. In the case of chlorides and bromides, zinc and cadmium halides form 1 : 1 complexes while mercury halides form 1 : 2 complexes with Bz_2S_2 . The iodides do not form any compound suggesting the weaker acceptor strength of the iodides. Molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions in dimethylformamide is < 5.0 mhos which rules out their ionic give evidence of dissociation but when additional ligand is present to reduce dissociation, the results (Table 1) suggest that the complexes are monomeric.

Information on the structure of these complexes has been derived from i.r. spectral studies, especially in the lower region. Pure Bz_2S_2 shows one intense absorption band at 1670 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 1750 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(C=O)$; a weak band at 520 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(S-S)$ and a sharp intense band at 670 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(C-S)$ ^{3,4}. The band originally present at 1750 cm^{-1} in Bz_2S_2 is shifted to 1655 cm^{-1} and the one at 1670 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1580 cm^{-1} on complex formation showing that in preference to S-S group, coordination takes place at C=O group. There is no significant change in the frequencies of C-S and S-S stretching modes. If the lowering of the carbonyl stretching mode on complex formation is measure of the acceptor strength of the metal halides, then these may be arranged in the following order as :

Strong new bands (not present in the free ligands) are observed in these adducts. These new bands are insensitive to the change of halogen for a particular metal and are therefore assigned as i.r. active M-O stretching vibration modes. In the case of zinc halide complexes⁵, it is observed at 410 cm^{-1} , at $\sim 360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of cadmium halide complexes⁶ and at $\sim 320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for mercury halide complexes⁷. Metal (II) oxygen modes usually occur below 500 cm^{-1} in many complexes of metal (II) salts with oxygen donor⁸⁻¹⁰.

In the far i.r spectra of the zinc complexes, strong bands are also observed at 300 cm^{-1} in the chloro and at 240 cm^{-1} in the bromo complexes which may be assigned to $\nu(Zn-Cl)$ and $\nu(Z-Br)$ stretching modes respectively and are in fair agreement to Zn-Cl and Zn-Br stretching modes in many other Zn (II) complexes known to have tetrahedral environment about the zinc atom¹¹. The bands at 260 cm^{-1} for chloro and at 220 cm^{-1} for bromo derivatives of cadmium halide complexes found in the same range as reported in literature^{12,13} suggest a tetrahedral structure for these metal halides adducts. Polymeric structures with halogen bridging are unlikely because they are associated with metal-halogen stretching modes at lower frequencies¹⁴. In the case of mercury (II) halide complexes, strong bands at 320 cm^{-1} for